
The Value of Time in the Creation of Historians

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ABSTRACT: This article discusses the Value of Time in the Creation of Historians. We will try to analyze this category on the example of Mu'izz ul-Ansab. The chronological data in the source are 146, of which 88 belong to the Genghis and 58 to the Timurid periods. We will analyze the chronological data according to the first stage of YOMIXT. The first of the numbers represents a data index belonging to the Genghis and the second to the Timurids.

KEYWORDS: Value of time, creation of historians, category, Mu'izz ul-Ansab, chronological data, Genghis, Timurid periods, index, Turkic, Chinese, Sogdian, Mongol, Arabic, Persian.

INTRODUCTION

In the texts of ancient Turkic, Chinese, Sogdian, Mongol, Arabic, Persian, Old Uzbek and Persian-Tajik sources of the VI-XIX centuries, the dates of historical events are in the Hijri year and month, in the AD year and month, with the names of Greek, Arabic and Iranian months, through the Turkish muchal, the names of the week, the time of prayers, the national calendar (Navruz, Navruz Khorezmshahi, Navruz Sultan), the symbols of the zodiac-constellations, etc. is given by [1:66-80]. Chronological data help to clarify the timing of historical events that took place and to systematically analyze a particular periodic boundary. This category makes up the bulk of the data in written sources. It should be noted that although most scientific studies provide chronological data on the history of a particular historical period or state [2], no serious attention has been paid to the complete analysis of chronological data in a single written source. It is advisable to divide the chronological information in a written source into three main types and variants according to the state of occurrence in the texts (There is no single typology in this category. It is advisable to divide the chronological data into different types and parts, depending on the lighting characteristics of the written source. (Comment by A. Bakiev, in the following lines A. B.):

THE MAIN FINDINGS AND RESULTS

I. Chronological data with clear dates:

- 1) The names of the weeks, days, months and dates of the Hijri year are shown together;
- 2) Information showing the dates of the day, month and Hijri year;
- 3) Information showing day, week names and hours;
- 4) Information showing the date, month and day status;
- 5) Information showing days, months and years of the year;
- 6) Information showing days and months;
- 7) Information showing the dates of the month and year;
- 8) Only date information is displayed;
- 9) Information showing only the date of the month;
- 10) Information specified in the alphabetical account;
- 11) Data with date only;
- 12) Information on how many years ago the incident took place;
- 13) Information on the age of a historical figure at the time of his death;
- 14) Information obtained at the beginning of the Hijri year;
- 15) Data showing the day of the week and the name of the month;

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16) And others (It is not possible to develop a perfect typology of chronological data in an article-level scientific study. Therefore, the phrase “And others” was used at the end of each type (A.B).

II. Chronological data with approximate dates:

- 1) Through the Turkish muchal;
- 2) With the names of the week;
- 3) With the time of prayers;
- 4) with the names of the Arabic months;
- 5) With the names of the Iranian months
- 6) People’s calendar (Navruz, Navruz Khorezmshahi, Navruz Sultan);
- 7) With the symbols of the zodiac-constellations;
- 8) Information that is additionally highlighted in the process of recording a historical event;
- 9) With the seasons;
- 10) with the year and seasons of the Turkish muchal;
- 11) The position of the Sun in the sky; 12) on the state of the seasons;
- 13) according to the Mongolian calendar;
- 14) by the names of the week and the status of the day;
- 15) And others.

III. Chronological data showing the duration of an event:

- 1) Periods of creative work;
- 2) Periods of construction of irrigation facilities;
- 3) Periods of detention of persons;
- 4) Periods of illness of individuals;
- 5) Periods of war;
- 6) Battle periods;
- 7) Periods of military march;
- 8) Periods of payment of salaries of soldiers;
- 9) Periods of sea voyages;
- 10) Different travel times;
- 11) Periods of siege;
- 12) Periods of conquest of a city, territory, castle, etc .;
- 13) Periods of harassment of members of other religions or non-believers;
- 14) Periods of various events;
- 15) Periods of Embassy;
- 16) Periods of religious ceremonies;
- 17) Periods of mourning ceremonies;
- 18) Periods of office of the persons;
- 19) Wintering periods;
- 20) Pasture periods;
- 21) Hunting periods;
- 22) Deadlines;
- 23) Periods of natural phenomena;
- 24) Periods of spread of a disease in the regions;
- 25) Periods of punishment;
- 26) Duration of a distance;
- 27) Periods of stay of individuals or the army;
- 28) Periods of guarding the army;
- 29) Information on the age of the historical person at the time of the incident;
- 30) The term of office of the rulers;
- 31) And others;

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Chronological data on the second type are given by the authors: "one day", "in a short time", "in the middle", "at this time", "in winter", "today", "the next day", "in the middle of the night", "Overnight", "morning", "after a while", "in the autumn of this year", "after a while", "About a year", "a few days later", "that night", "until the horses get fat", "in the morning", "at night", "tomorrow at dawn", "this year", "this month", "born at the time of death", "within two or three days", "after two or three days", "in the spring of the year of the sheep", "about seventy-five days", "the spring of the year of the pig", "during this period", "Two hundred years ago", "When the solar eclipse reaches the point of equinox in spring", "after winter and the spring of the year of the mouse", "in the first spring of the year of the sheep", "for several years", "on a certain day", "in the year of the bear", "leopard after three months of siege", "their governments lasted five hundred and twenty-three years", "they lived forty-eight years", "Seventeen years as khan", "a few months ago", "in a week", "at the end of this month", "on the ninth of the month", "for thirty years", "at the end of Ramadan", "zu-l-hijja", "in the middle", "some time", "right now", "these days", "at the end of this month", "this year", "Since the time of the terrible event", "in the middle of winter", "Eid", "next day", "last year", "several years", "in those days", "at the end of winter", "three days", "after", "for a period", "at the end of one day", "for a period of three years", "for two months", "the date of that opportunity is up to nine hundred and eight", "for this opportunity", "how many times", "at the end of time", "Since the oath", "five months of the fortress", "ul fatarotta", "earlier", "in this history", "how many years", "until the end of the oath", "three or four years ago", "Samarkand was the second", "In turn", "How many years", "At that time", "At the end of this month", "Evening prayer in the middle of the night", "Late prayer in another", "In this winter", "In four or five years in the Kazakhs", "that time" and in sentences indicating the approximate time of the historical event (The pages of the books were not shown as these quotations were taken in a mixed form from a number of written sources (A.B). We will try to analyze this category on the example of Mu'izz ul-Ansab [3]. The chronological data in the source are 146, of which 88 belong to the Genghis and 58 to the Timurid periods. We will analyze the chronological data according to the first stage of YOMIXT [4] (The first of the numbers represents a data index belonging to the Genghis and the second to the Timurids. The types and types of chronological data may vary depending on the nature of the data available in the source under study (A.B):

- a) Information on the dates of birth of household members: 2=11;
- b) Information on the dates of accession of the representatives of the house: 28=0;
- c) Information on the terms of the throne of the representatives of the household who came to power: 14=1;
- d) Information on the age at which household representatives died: 1=37;
- e) Information on the dates of death of the representatives of the household: 33=8;
- f) Chronological data on various historical processes: 10=0.

If we analyze the chronological data found in Mu'izz ul-Ansab on the basis of types, it turns out that 78 of them (59 = 19) are clearly dated, and the remaining 68 (29 = 39) are approximate chronological data (A three-step systematic analysis of the data on dates in Mu'izz al-Ansab requires separate research. Since it is not possible to cover this issue fully in one article, we will leave the analysis to further research (A.B).

Reasons for the diversity of chronological information in written sources:

- The beginning of historical periods in nations at different times;
- Availability of different calendars;
- The authors of the written source received extracts from the published written sources using different calendars;
- The fact that the authors of the written source were forced to set approximate chronological dates because they covered the historical events that took place long after that;
- Authors of written sources in the process of covering historical events, although not widely used at the time, used local accounts of the year in which they were born and raised locally;

The authors of the source used various chronological expressions to cover the events. It is also natural that this situation is difficult for the researcher or students to understand. Understanding chronological terms and phrases requires a certain skill and knowledge on the part of the researcher. This chronological typology has been developed to facilitate this process as much as possible. This chronological typology helps researchers using sources to accurately visualize the time and place of events.

REFERENCES

- 1) Historical thinking. A collection of scientific works of historians of the Republic, dedicated to the Year of harmoniously developed generation. Buxoro. 2010, P. 66-80.
- 2) Bikerman E. Chronology of the ancient world. M., Nauka, 1975, 336 p.; Important dates in world history (from the most ancient times to the present day) / Q. Rajabov [et al.]; responsible editors R. Farmonov, Ch. Kucharov.-Tashkent:

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- Uzbekistan, 2011.-P.616; World history in dates and events. Translated from French by V. Rummyantsev. -Moscow: "Rainbow", 2002; The World History. T. 1 - 1 3. -M.: State publishing house of political literature .- "Mysl", 1955-1983. [T.1-10; 1955-1965; T.11-13: 1977-1983.]; The World History. Encyclopedia. Under the general editorship of V. Makarovich and others- Moscow: Great Russian Encyclopedia, 2003.; Rajabov K, Hasanov F., Shoymardonov I., Tojiboev B. Important dates in the history of Uzbekistan (from ancient times to the present day). Z-edition.- Tashkent: "Uzbekistan", 2010; Stanley Lan-Poole. Muslim dynasties. - Moscow - Tashkent - Bishkek: "Turkestan", 1996; Choriev 3.Tarih atamalarining qisqacha izokhli lu'fatlari. 2-nashri.- Tashkent: "Academy"2002.;
- 3) Mu'izz al-ansab (Glorifying genealogy). Introduction, translation from Persian, notes, preparation of facsimiles for publication by Sh.Kh. Vohidova // History of Kazakhstan in Persian Sources. Volume III, Almaty: Dyk - Press,2006. – P. 672.
 - 4) Boqiev A.A. et al. The first comments on the "Information-technological map of the written source" (VI-XIX centuries) // Historical thinking. A collection of scientific and practical articles by historians. Volume VII. - Tashkent, New Century Generation.2015. P. 41-62.